

INDEPENDENT LEARNING THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES: OPPORTUNITIES, BARRIERS, AND SOCIAL STRATIFICATION

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Annotation: This article analyzes the concept of autonomy shaped by digital technologies in relation to social disparities, technical biographies, and implicit skills. It provides empirical examples demonstrating that digital teaching practices – particularly those involving innovative approaches – are not equally effective for all social groups.

Keywords: Autonomy, digital inequality, technical biography, digital entrepreneurship, social determinants, innovative pedagogy, digital skills.

The notion of autonomy appears frequently throughout the analyses presented in this collection. However, this interpretation differs significantly from the one found in the sociology of professions or within the realm of artistic and cultural production [1]. Those perspectives often emphasize the construction of social spheres or communities governed by their own internal logic.

In contrast, the concept of autonomy discussed in these articles diverges from philosophical or political viewpoints that regard it as an ideal educational objective, or from pedagogical positions that see it as a central instructional goal. Rather, in this context, autonomy is approached more as a skill to be cultivated or an individual capacity to be strengthened.

Such a form of autonomy often emerges in the absence of external guidance, supervision, or control – conditions typically associated with a learner's novice status. Limiting this external guidance encourages independent engagement with both the activity itself and the learning processes surrounding it. Accordingly, the conceptualization of autonomy featured in these contributions aligns more closely with constructivist educational theories, where learning is grounded in active participation, learner engagement, and personal responsibility [2].

Sociological research has already demonstrated that autonomy within educational settings is deeply influenced by underlying social inequalities [3]. However, efforts to foster such autonomy are primarily carried out through pedagogical innovations, particularly those involving the integration of digital technologies.

Social Profiles and Technological Biographies. The articles included in this thematic volume offer valuable insights into how certain populations either possess or are deprived of “autonomy” in their engagement with digital technologies, and how such conditions are often presented as natural or self-evident. In digital learning contexts, not only do pre-existing social determinants resurface, but these studies also illustrate how mediation through digital tools can actually intensify the influence of these determinants by reinforcing the relationship between technical practices and socially constructed imaginaries.

Individuals’ capacity to interact with digital technologies – as well as the types of usage and competencies made available to them – are closely tied to broader factors such as age (youth or old age), gender, and socio-cultural background. Access and adaptability are rarely neutral, as they often reflect existing structural advantages or limitations.

Moreover, the articles also shed light on the political dimensions of digital teaching systems. These systems may either reproduce or challenge prevailing social imaginaries, thereby impacting users differently depending on their social positioning – sometimes reinforcing the status quo, sometimes offering opportunities for transformation.

Social Stratification of Digital Practices. Early research has already highlighted how inequities in access to, usage of, and autonomy over digital technologies are shaped by broader patterns of social stratification [4]. However, there remains a lack of in-depth empirical studies exploring how digital skills, autonomy, and competencies actually develop, how these processes intersect with individuals’ socio-professional profiles and technical biographies, and how they are influenced – or constrained – by age- and gender-based social expectations and stereotypes.

The first two articles in this collection offer original and complementary perspectives on these issues. They analyze the dynamics of digital autonomy and skill acquisition by examining two contrasting social groups: one where individuals are characterized by limited digital competence and autonomy, and another where these attributes are considered relatively strong. Through this comparison, the studies shed light on the mechanisms through which digital inequalities are both reproduced and potentially challenged.

Gabrielle Lavenir’s Study. Gabrielle Lavenir analyzes findings from a qualitative investigation based on interviews and observations conducted with individuals over the age of sixty. Drawing on rich and original fieldwork, her research uncovers the key factors influencing how older adults engage with

digital technologies, offering nuanced insights into the digital experiences of this age group.

The author identifies three primary areas of tension:

A longstanding history of technology use, which is often overlooked by initiatives aimed at improving digital literacy among older adults;

Changing physical abilities, which may hinder elderly users from effectively interacting with digital devices;

Weak social networks, which limit access to resources and support for learning digital technologies.

Special attention is given to digital training programs offered in nursing homes and elder care institutions (EHPADs). The study emphasizes a disconnect between prevailing social representations and the lived technological experiences – or "technobiographies" [5] – of older individuals, highlighting how standardized narratives often fail to capture the complexity of their actual engagement with digital tools.

What Kind of Learning Preparation Is Needed to Become a Digital Entrepreneur? One of the central themes explored in this special issue concerns the relationship between learners' dispositions toward learning and the technical or informational tools (i.e., digital systems) they engage with. Several articles uncover the implicit assumptions that underlie common narratives linking digital entrepreneurship with digital tools and skill acquisition.

Despite extensive data on inequalities in digital access and usage [6], digital technologies are frequently framed as offering a "second chance" – particularly for economically disadvantaged individuals or those seeking to reorient their professional paths. In this context, digital tools are often promoted as effective entry points for beginners, especially in pathways leading toward entrepreneurship.

Within this issue, two articles focus specifically on the gap between the theoretical characteristics of officially designated target populations and the often unspoken, pre-existing skills and competencies implicitly required by digital platforms and systems. These contributions reveal that prior knowledge and cultural capital continue to play a crucial role in determining individuals' ability to successfully engage in digital learning and entrepreneurial activities.

On Fabien Labarthe's Research. In his article, Fabien Labarthe revisits the study of computer science from a narrowly focused educational perspective. He examines training programs in informatics that are built upon so-called "innovative" pedagogical approaches. These courses are implemented within

institutions such as France's Grande École du Numérique, which are specifically designed to promote inclusivity by reaching learners from diverse social and educational backgrounds.

Labarthe o'z tadqiqotida ushbu muassasa doirasida shakllangan rasmiy bayonot va shiorlarni emas, balki bu g'oyalar qanday amaliyotga tatbiq etilishini aniq faktlar asosida tahlil qiladi. U turli auditoriyalar (o'quvchi guruhlarida) innovatsion pedagogikaning qanday qabul qilinishiga e'tibor qaratadi. Tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatadiki, bu ta'lim yondashuvi barcha o'quvchilar uchun birdek muvaffaqiyatli bo'la olmaydi.

Building on Nicolas Auray's [7] concept of "computer science virtuosos" – individuals who operate in self-directed, exploratory learning modes – Labarthe critically examines the social and educational competencies associated with such profiles. His analysis leads to a striking conclusion: contrary to the initial inclusive intentions, these innovative and autonomy-driven pedagogical formats often present the greatest challenges for learners with limited academic preparation.

Conclusion. This thematic collection explores the concept of autonomy in digital learning through the lens of social inequality, technological biographies, and pedagogical approaches. Unlike traditional frameworks where autonomy is treated as an ideal state, the articles here view it as an individual skill to be developed and reinforced. Furthermore, the findings reveal a critical paradox: while innovative educational methods involving digital technologies may offer new opportunities for some social groups, they can also create additional barriers for others, depending on their prior educational background and access to cultural or technical capital.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. SAPIRO Gisèle (2019). « Repenser le concept d'autonomie pour la sociologie des biens symboliques », *Biens Symboliques / Symbolic Goods*, (4).
2. BARBOT Marie-José & TRÉMION Virginie (2016). « De l'émancipation à l'autonomie : stabilisation et ouverture de possibles », *Recherches & éducations*, (16), pp. 21-34.
3. GASPARINI Rachel, JOLY-RISSOAN Odile & DALUD-VINCENT Monique (2009). « Variations sociales des représentations de l'autonomie dans le travail scolaire chez les collégiens et lycéens », *Revue française de pédagogie*, 168, pp. 93-109.
4. HARGITTAI Eszter & HSIEH Yuli Patrick (2013). *Digital Inequality* (William H Dutton, Dir). Oxford University Press, Vol. 1..
5. BUSE Christina E. (2010). "E-scaping the ageing body? Computer technologies and embodiment in later life", *Ageing and Society*, 30 (6), pp. 987-1009.

6. HARGITTAI Eszter & HSIEH Yuli Patrick (2013). Digital Inequality (William H Dutton, Dir). Oxford University Press, Vol. 1.
7. AURAY Nicolas (2016). L'alerte ou l'enquête : une sociologie pragmatique du numérique. Paris, Presses des Mines-Transvalor.

